

Portraying theory and practice of University Social Responsibility through through a Joint International MOOC

In 2018 the Universities in the University Social Responsibility Network embarked on the ambitious project of creating a collaborative Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) aiming to raise awareness of the concept of USR, boost visibility of the achievements and social impacts members in the network have in their communities, and promote effective strategies for design and implementation of the universities' civic engagements. The paper describes the construction process of the MOOC Introduction to USR, jointly produced by Kyoto University and The Hong Kong Polytechnic University, with cooperation from members of the USRN, and hosted at edX platform. The following pages depict the consensus building process, in what way commitment from the USRN members was secured, how each contributing institution brought their share to the project and how those pieces were stitched together. The paper explains some of the challenges faced and how they were overcome, lessons learned and tips for success are shared for future reference.

Implication for practice or policy

- The paper describes the process, implications of multilateral engagements, and production of a collaborative MOOC from where suggestions for similar endeavors can be drawn.
- The paper focuses on the need for university managers to raise visibility of their USR institutional engagements, activities and programs as part of their third mission.
- The paper invites university managers to consider strategies in universities to *do the work!* *show the work!* and *work the show*.

Keywords: USR, multilateral collaboration, MOOC production, University Social Responsibility Network, policy making, social engagement, case study

Introduction

Context

With the growth of economical and societal challenges, universities can no longer afford to be solely involved in producing human capital or equipping their graduates with knowledge and skills. Nor can they continue to carry out research that is not actively and consciously responsible to meet and address social needs and expectations. Universities are rapidly called on to focus on and be engaged with what is usually referred to as the university's *third mission* or more recently as University Social Responsibility or *USR* (Tetrevova & Sabolova, 2010; Chen, Nasongkhla, & Donaldson, 2015).

Universities need to expand the application of education and research beyond academic environments. They can no longer remain an *ivory tower*, where only scientists and intellectuals create, seize, and profit from knowledge. They are now expected to open up, reach out, and engage with society organically; universities are expected to put the accumulated knowledge and know-how to the service of society to contribute to social welfare of society at large.

USR can be defined as a shared responsibility across universities to address real social challenges and in turn advancing different societies and communities. According to Shek and Hollister (2017), USR is realized through shaping policies that center the integration of the concept in all the missions and duties of the university. Through USR practices, universities can reinforce their roles in society by enhancing their responsibility, promoting ethics, and encouraging good citizenship (Alzyoud and Bani-Hani, 2015). Civil citizenship, civic engagement, and voluntary contributions of academia is also focused by Vasilescu et al. (2010) as steps toward fulfilling sustainability.

In line with this vision, the University Social Responsibility Network (USRN) is a platform that brings together institutions from around the world to consolidate and expand the scope of action and impact of the two traditional missions of universities (education and research) to address economic, social, and environmental problems. The network shares features with the Talloires Network, an important predecessor (see Hollister et al., 2012 for more details on Talloires Network), as they both serve as platforms to develop synergies and boost cooperation among universities (University Social Responsibility Network, n.d.).

The USRN was established in 2015 by The Hong Kong Polytechnic University, bringing together university leaders committed to making the world more just and peaceful; to making societies more inclusive, and to contributing to sustainable development. The USRN promotes a proactive mindset among members on how to engage with and give back to society. In the long run, activities of the network are expected to positively impact universities in the recruitment of motivated students and researchers, foster and empower proactive partnerships with other universities and institutions, and strengthen universities' evidence at the time of seeking funding.

As of March 2021, the USRN consists of 16 reputable institutions due to their work and commitment to USR worldwide. These universities have a well established record of designing and implementing programs that bridge the gap between academic knowledge and social demands. They remain committed to raising awareness about the importance of giving back to society, promoting socially relevant research and making it accessible to society at large. They also continue to engage in partnering within and outside the USRN to steer the global discussion about USR (Shek & Hollister, 2017).

To raise visibility of the USRN's achievements, and to showcase good practices in civic engagement among members, Kyoto University and The Hong Kong Polytechnic University decided to create a collaborative Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) to introduce University Social Responsibility. This paper describes the process behind the making of this MOOC.

Collaborative MOOCs and their development

As online education gained prominence and credibility, more universities jumped on the bandwagon and started publicizing their content and materials. With this unprecedented opportunity, universities could now build and maintain their own branding, taking advantage of analyzing the big data and drawing outcomes that could serve into improving on-campus teaching and learning.

Rapid advancement of communication technologies continue to boost online education, and MOOCs are not an exception. While technology has made it possible for more personalization and diversity among MOOCs (Hood & Littlejohn, 2016), the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic has clearly further boosted the interest in these courses and their potentials (Jonathan Haber, 2020; Chris Impley, 2021).

After a decade, universities remain the major providers of MOOCs. They offer subjects and academic contents to equip learners with skills and knowledge usually engaged in higher education. Within this context, online education has continued to grow and develop in the booming number of new courses made available, and in the scope of their fields, the different combinations of instructional models, and their pedagogical frameworks (McAndrew & Scanlon, 2013; McClure, 2013).

However, universities are not the solo players in this arena. Online education providers have partnered with other non-academic organizations. These partnerships take place at various levels, considering the participants' and the providers needs and expectations. According to Shumski (2013), Coursera, another prominent MOOC provider at an international scope, engaged in a partnership with the United States government to create free courses together with in-person discussion with the aim of exposing foreign educators to American education. While at a more local level, JMOOC in Japan brings together a wide range of providers (JMOOC: Schools & Partners, n.d.).

It is not surprising that MOOCs attract more educators and learners in the strive for professional and personal development than ever before. In a research on analyzing the effects of MOOC on teachers and Learners' on developing different sets of skills, Viswanathan (2012) concludes that MOOC can be utilized as a means of teachers' professional development and constantly upgrading knowledge of specific areas. while Florentine (2015) argues that

MOOCs are *differentiators* for professional development due to cost-effectiveness, ease of access, content carefully composed by subjects, and because they can be reviewed by stakeholders. MOOCs have potential for collaboration and they can function as hubs, where educators can upgrade their skills through easier and cheaper exchanges and interactions with others.

Sammour, Al-zoubi, and Schreurs (2019) believe that MOOCs serve as platforms where universities can enhance international and domestic collaborations. Joint academic endeavors lead to superior educational outcomes because they can rely on experience and expertise of all parties involved. Sammour et al. (2019) and also Culver et al. (2012) suggest that a good model are the *Virtual Joint Academic Degree* programs, which are created to cultivate the learning experience in an enhanced international setting, and to attach more international visibility and recognition to the institutions offering them.

Joint MOOCs enhance quality assurance through sharing high quality content among university members in different alliances. The Asia-Europe Meeting (ASEM) Network of Massive Open Online Courses is a coalition that creates courses aiming to strengthen dialogue and cooperation between Asia and Europe, in political, economic, socio-cultural and educational dimensions (Asia-Europe Meeting: ASEM Education. 2017, accessed March 2021). Another example is the UNA Europa's *Joint-micro credentials* which helps make transition from Bachelor to Master easier for those switching their fields of study. The *partial master* program hinges on a series of MOOCs that are jointly offered and accredited by UNA partners. (Futures, Andersen, & Larsen, December 2020).

It is in the context of international academic collaboration that the current paper describes the creation of this MOOC, launched in February during the USRN Summit organized by University of Pretoria in South Africa and covered by the *University World News* (Kigotho, February 3, 2021).

Research purpose, objectives and method

Online education and university civic engagement are gaining momentum, their relevance is expected to continue to grow, consolidate and have deeper implications for the future. Still, research on the two areas –USR and joint MOOCs– is scarce in the literature.

As described by Hersh and Schneider (2005), even if universities put forward in their mission statements the commitment to educate morally responsible and intellectually competent individuals, in reality, the focus on equipping students with intellectual skills usually surpasses the goal of nurturing graduates with a strong ethical and empathetic sense, intentionally and proficiently built into their curricula and research.

Now more than ever, universities are called to *do the work, show the work, and work the show* (Palacio & Choy, 2019). Throughout history universities have made outstanding contributions in the work they have traditionally done, focusing on teaching and research. In the last few decades, two new concepts have been added to the understanding of what universities' mission should be: the need to give back to society and having efficient management systems to address their operations effectively.

The *do the work* part of universities' mission has always been there, however as university rankings became more decisive and influential, they have made it clear that universities *too* need to be accountable for what they do for society at large, and hence the need for universities to start *showing the work*. It is the very game of rankings that is pushing the universities to develop their strategies to *work their show*.

This paper is a descriptive account of the experience of envisioning, designing and executing a multilateral collaborative MOOC on USR. As such, it contributes to the development of the literature because it describes the process of creation of a multilateral collaborative MOOC that addresses USR and showcases good practices in civic engagement. Both the MOOC itself as well as its contents address some of the challenges universities face when embarking on international academic collaboration.

Based on observations during the project, the paper provides an overview of the process of consensus building among USRN members to create a collaborative MOOC; it shows how individual contributions not only added to the whole of the course, but also how universities can showcase their own forte when it comes to USR activities.

The following pages explain how the pieces were gathered and stitched together, while highlighting the different dimensions in the process including some of the challenges, lessons learned, and finally sharing key final outcomes.

Pondering a MOOC on USR: multiple solutions in one shot

In December 2018, USRN members gathered for the *Critical Hope USRN Summit* in Haifa University, to share their contributions on conflict resolution and community engagement. Representatives agreed to foster cooperation and on the need to raise visibility of the network, its achievements and relevance, while underscoring the importance of synergy in the USR work carried out by each university in a joint effort.

Based on the accord that USR is complex and that understanding of the concept varies among managers and administrators depending on the contexts and institutional priorities, the network decided to create a MOOC to bring together accumulated knowledge among the members, share their experiences, and consolidate strategies for successful design of USR plans. The MOOC shows that USR should be understood as an umbrella covering diverse institutional approaches while addressing wide social and environmental needs and expectations.

A joint MOOC was envisioned as a feasible, yet, inclusive and easy-to-implement project: addressing diversity of contexts, regional membership distribution and priorities, while sharing the common goals of promoting civic engagement of universities, and making the design and implementation of USR activities more efficient. This MOOC is an appropriate response from universities in a moment when, as described by Hersh and Schneider (2005), there is a need to reconsider what teaching and research mean, while looking at how to create fully developed humans, and how universities nurture commitment to freedom and tolerance, and raise awareness of the need to work in an interdependent and concerted fashion.

With the leadership of Kyoto University and Hong Kong Polytechnic University, as partners of edX, a world renown platform for MOOCs, members of the USRN agreed to share their experiences as videos and reading materials. The MOOC aims to: (a) increase global knowledge of USR and gain support for the USR movement; (b) foster universities' understanding and engagement with USR; (c) disseminate successful practices and strategies; and (d) promote international exchange and collaboration.

Enacting the collaboration in USRN

USRN Secretary focal point

The USRN Secretary functioned as the focal point and had a key role in recruiting the contributors and also managing logistics and distribution of tasks; the process started by explaining the project and requesting collaboration from all members.

With a well-balanced regional representation, universities that joint the project include: Kyoto University (Japan), University of New South Wales (Australia), Simon Fraser University (Canada), The Hong Kong Polytechnic University (Hong Kong), TUFTS University (USA), University of Manchester (UK), University of Pretoria (South Africa), and University of São Paulo (Brazil).

Other members expressed interest, however the time frame did not allow them to gather the information as requested, and thus a follow up or a second MOOC to include other contributions has been under consideration. At the time of writing this paper (March 2021), this remains to be decided.

Drafting the overall MOOC at Kyoto University

With the consent of the USRN Secretariat, the production team at Kyoto University drafted the initial structure for the course including a theoretical framework on key features of USR, and how the concrete cases provided by the participating universities should be embedded in the overall context of the MOOC.

A guideline for contributing universities was shared containing goals of the project, and details of how it would be implemented. Specific explanations referred to the formats of those contributions, including time allotments, overall format of each case (as in introduction, core USR, outcomes), and also technical specifications regarding the quality of videos and other extra materials. To maintain consistency, universities were requested to follow a clear map of what information was necessary and how each case should be presented. A suggested format was shared for contributors to build up their cases (see: Suggested format for cases and mini cases. Image1).

Image1. Suggested format for cases and mini cases.

The guideline describes all steps of the project together with the structure of the four-week MOOC. It explains the logistics as well as how each contributing university should generate its own case. Each contributor was in charge of mobilizing its resources and producing its own materials. Once ready, these materials were collected through the USRN secretariat and shared with the team at Kyoto University for integration, editing and revision.

Although a timeline had been agreed, expecting to collect all data by February 2020 so that the building of the MOOC could get started, a number of factors delayed the the process including: (a) gathering information within each university; (b) production of materials; (c) sharing with the Secretariat and compilation by the Kyoto University team; and (d) the start of the SARS-Cov-2 pandemic.

Balance in the contributions reaching consensus on formats and contents

Contributing universities and the USRN as whole, have relevant programs that reflect civic engagement with their respective communities. Therefore, at the time of developing the structure of the course, it was important to balance not only each of these universities' approaches to USR but also their examples and how they portray their stories.

The MOOC is organized as a 4 weeks course, each containing 80 to 90 minute worth of video lectures. The first week presents the history and the underpinning theory of USR, together with manifestations of USR and some background on the USRN. The second and third weeks showcase *USR in action*; through information shared by the universities presented as *cases* and *mini cases* that portray institutional approaches to the USR and tell their stories. Cases consisting of approximately 40 minutes showing broader approaches or activities, while mini cases were allocated 15 minutes, to share more in-focus stories of specific programs.

The fourth week consists of one more mini case and strategies for success in design and expansion of USR as part of the theoretical approach, giving the visual idea of a *sandwich*. In other words, weeks one and four, are theory-based and wrap over weeks two and three that showcase practices.

Image2. Sandwich structure of the whole MOOC.

(see: Image 2. Sandwich structure of the whole MOOC).

Cases included the Mandatory service learning program at The Hong Kong Polytechnic University; The University of Manchester's decision to make USR a core institutional priority and its flagship programs; and the Kyoto University case showing a multidisciplinary and multi-layered approach to USR ranging from small individual programs, Department-level programs, multi-department level programs, university wide programs and university wide programs with international and multilateral collaboration.

Mini cases consisted of University of São Paulo on its strategy for social inclusion through arts and culture; Simon Fraser University on engagement with local communities and revisions of their institutional procedures in procurement and purchasing; University of New South Wales on policies for gender equity regarding recruiting and contracts; and, University of Pretoria on their social engagement and student volunteering program in Engineering.

Special thoughts on the audience of the MOOC

Enrollment was open to the general public, but unlike other MOOCs developed to attract more traditional learners, this course on *Introduction to USR* targets faculty, staff, and especially, university managers since these are typically the people in charge of designing and implementing policy at the university level. This decision affected the evaluation procedures in the course, as problem sets were limited to quizzes that aim not only at checking knowledge retention but more importantly to reinforce understanding.

Diversity and unity of USR approaches

There exists wide diversity regarding the meaning of what USR is. Universities have different approaches to and ways of understanding their policies and projects through which they serve their communities. As mentioned in the introduction, there is not consensus among scholars on what such a definition should be.

For example, according to Shek and Hollister (2017, p. 13), for example, “acknowledging that USR is a wide-ranging and evolving concept, which is open to interpretations, we propose, in its broad meaning, that university social responsibility could be understood as the responsibility shared by universities in contributing to social betterment through the integration of social responsibility policies into institutional management, teaching, research, services and public activities.”

For this project, addressing this diversity was challenging because what contributing universities put forth as projects and programs highly depends on the context and nature of the social issues surrounding the society or community that the university identifies with. However, all of these endeavors, in their own right, contribute to the betterment of society; and with this in mind the MOOC was envisioned to function as an inclusive and *binding umbrella*.

In order to connect all the diversity of approaches and cases together, a binding script was created and put together through a series of videos to make the content of the course more interconnected and meaningful.

Internal and external quality assurance

The contents of the MOOC are categorized into videos, reading materials, and quizzes. The first two were produced by each university whereas the latter was produced by the Kyoto University team and confirmed with each respective contributor. To ensure quality, once pieces were assembled, a second round of internal consultations was held with the USRN Secretariat and contributing members, and externally with edX as the hosting platform of the MOOC.

The first draft of the materials and proposals for each case and mini case were shared with and reviewed by the Kyoto University team and the USRN Secretariat to verify the relevance of contents and on the uniqueness of the cases. The Kyoto University team made suggestions and upon this feedback, each contributing university made the final editing changes and proceeded with producing their own materials.

Aiming to assure a unified approach to quality and format within edX platform's requirements, for assessment of learning outcomes, the team at Kyoto University drafted the quizzes based on the contents provided by each university. The Hong Kong Polytechnic University team suggested ways to improve and add variety to the format so as to encourage learners' more active engagement. Once the drafts were ready, they were shared with each contributing university to solicit feedback and suggestions.

Distribution and accessibility

edX platform is an open source platform that disseminates MOOCs from prominent universities and accommodates a large crowd of providers and learners at a global scale. Embracing this quality meant a great opportunity to make the course accessible beyond the USRN members to include faculty staff and senior management who are interested in learning about the nuances of different USR related activities in different institutions and geographical regions.

The course *Introduction to USR* is hosted in the edX platform and respectively on Kyoto University's KyotoUx, and Hong Kong Polytechnic University's PolyUx. In order to accommodate all stakeholders, a special website was created within edX showing the names of both organizations providing the course jointly; this in turn means that the name of the course itself was coded to allow both universities to host it on their respective sites.

The MOOC is unique in that not only it is the ever first attempt to introduce the USR concept and showcasing the outstanding practices through a global platform like edX, and it being released under the two university's branding schemes.

A trailer was created by the Kyoto University team, covering the highlights from the course to be distributed on edX platform and beyond as an embedded YouTube video. The trailer was reviewed and verified by relevant stakeholders later.

Promotion and dissemination of the MOOC started by using the websites of the USRN as well as those of each individual university. Dissemination was conducted through channels such as Newsletters, internal mailing systems and networks, social media, USRN itself, reaching out for social media, and related organizations such as ministries of education and other educational institutions.

Challenges and lessons learned from the project

Due to its collaborative nature, the production of the MOOC faced various challenges at the network level including relations in and outside the USRN, diversity of contents and approaches, institutional commitment; at the human level, which refers to personal and institutional support, understanding of what MOOC and USR are; and lastly at the dispersion of materials, mainly relating to production, quality, and contents.

At the network level

Consensus on the goals of MOOC. At first it had seemed obvious, however having members agree on the expected achievements through this project was not easy. Once members were unanimous on the goals of the course –(a) contributing to raising awareness of USR; (b) raising visibility of the USRN; and (c) fostering interest among universities for their civic engagement– the actual design and production started.

Deciding the targeted audience. Different from other MOOCs it became clear that people who would be interested in this project were a specific kind of learners. The course does not target the general public but a niche: university managers and academic staff with interest in promoting university social engagement.

Defining structure and contents. Addressing theory and practical implications of USR and the diversity in the information to be shared represented a challenge at the time of balancing the contributions from the network as compared to those made by individual members. This resulted in the sandwich structure presented in 3.3. (Balance in the contributions reaching consensus on formats and contents)

Distribution of tasks. Allocation of efforts for production represented an important challenge. Although at the time of discussion with other members on creating the MOOC, many of them showed support, when distributing the tasks and commencing on the actual production the much of the initial passionate support faded.

Funding & resources. One of the most interesting aspects of the project is its collaborative nature, hence putting the necessary resources together from each contributing member brought its own piece to the table. As in a potluck, each party was in charge of designing and producing its own piece. The USRN Secretariat's leadership brought those resources together, while each contributing university produced and provided its own contents, and the Kyoto University team stitched all the pieces together.

Relation with EdX. Although collaborative MOOCs have been produced in the past, they have typically been bilateral efforts. This MOOC gathers a wide number of contributors. The variety of stakeholders made it challenging to decide who should lead negotiations and exchanges with edX and who should host the course. It was agreed that because the Hong Kong Polytechnic University and Kyoto University are edX members, and they already have courses on the platform, they should take the lead. This resulted in an integrated approach from the USRN, where Kyoto University acted as the representative of the network in the exchanges with edX.

Copyrights and ownership. Some members raised concerns about copyright and ownership of the materials shared through the MOOC. Although initially not considered as a major problem, issues over copyright and ownership resulted in some members having to drop out although they had originally been expected to participate. The overall solution found among the contributing parties later was that information and cases presented in the MOOC would belong to the USRN and Edx.

At the human level

Internal & external reach out. Gathering material for the course showed challenges on two fronts: from the universities as a whole, and from individual contributors in each university. Securing engagement required more networking than expected. This became evident when needing to explain the project to people who are unfamiliar with USR or MOOC; delivering the message and inviting them to share or produce materials was time-consuming for the Kyoto University team and the representatives.

Commitment and promises. Most member universities announced their interest at the start of the process, maintaining that they would share unique USR perspectives or programs. However, it became clear that not all participants could actually share that information, hence there was a need to compensate for them, this proved challenging in terms of balance of the whole structure and specifics for each kind of USR activities. Examples include approaches to SDGs or on conflict management and peace building.

Participation and commitment overtime. Some members showed strong commitment to the project in the beginning, however as management changed in the universities that support dropped. One more factor that affected the project was the spread of the COVID-19 pandemic. This had a deep impact on all aspects of the production of the MOOC since universities were overwhelmed addressing the pandemic.

Personal & institutional support. Commitment to the MOOC and to the USRN as a whole among members varied greatly through the process. Universities such as The Hong Kong Polytechnic University showed full institutional support to both the network and the course whereas in other universities there have been very active and engaged individuals, that however lack support from their own faculties or universities. In the middle, there are institutions that offer support through specific departments but not the university as a whole. Managing the diversity in commitment and support required an extra effort from the production team of the course. A solution to this was being flexible and allowing each participant to contribute with the best of their resources and experiences.

Knowledge about USR and MOOC. Another challenge was the different levels of awareness about university social responsibility, what it means, and how it works; while there were also clear differences in understanding of what a MOOC is, how it is created, and how it works. Producing the Guideline (explained in 3.2) helped not only spread awareness on the relevance of the project, but also explain with a level of detail why this is important and what was expected to be done.

About dispersion of materials

Although a detailed explanation of the expected contents and formats of the materials was shared as guidelines and sent to all contributing members, some submitted their materials using different formats or contents that were different from what had been agreed. This led to new rounds of negotiations to accommodate all contributions in a way that made sense in the overall structure of the course.

Quality of materials. What defines quality across universities is not always consistent. Although the Kyoto University team shared the guidelines with all contributing universities at the start of the project, what was received as a final result, sometimes, differed with the initial expectations from the production team. Follow-up email correspondence and orientation meetings with each respective university upon their request served to reach a consensus on the quality.

Pace of production. Contributions from universities were expected to follow an initially agreed timeline, however submissions did actually happen over a longer than expected period of time. This clearly slowed down the pace of the whole project, which was even further affected with the outbreak of the pandemic.

Diversity of Content

Diversity of contents. One of the most thought-provoking challenges faced was that the production team needed to address a wide range of diversity with regard to how universities think of and implement USR. Creating a map of USR areas describing the kind of initiatives helped putting this *constellation of contributions* in a logical framework for the MOOC as a whole.

Global representation. The USRN has members from all continents and this global presence was to be evidenced through the cases shared in the MOOC. Some of the problems universities address through their USR engagement are of global significance, while certain initiatives address issues of local importance. Hence planning the allocation of time to each piece in the structure of the course was sensitive, yet essential.

To address this problem, contributions were organized as cases and mini cases, and they were grouped based on the relation among their contents. The Hong Kong Polytechnic University and the University of Manchester shared *cases* portraying engagements of more global nature; while University of São Paulo, University of Pretoria, Simon Fraser University and New South Wales University shared a more locally focused kind of initiatives. Lastly, Kyoto University opted for a mix in its approach, blending together regional and local activities.

Internal balance. Depending on the nature of each contribution, cases and mini cases were grouped to support and to serve as examples to each other, by showing USR activities of similar nature. The challenge here was how to embed cases and mini cases in a way that would preserve the balance within the course. For example, some of the mini cases contained a brief description of *that* University's USR activities while demonstrating the uniqueness and significance of what they do.

Telling the whole story. The MOOC was conceived to integrate theory and practice, introducing general elements of USR while looking at concrete lessons learned from projects and closing up with tips for success. Bringing the pieces together in an integrated course was achieved through fluid communication with all contributing members with the leadership from the USRN Secretariat at The Hong Kong Polytechnic University and the Kyoto University team.

Collaboration with edX. The collaborative and multilateral nature of the MOOC needed attention regarding the relation with edX, since the platform would have to agree to a jointly hosted course that would be accessible from the portals of two different universities: KyotoUx and HKPolyUx. This, in turn, brought unforeseen challenges relating to copyrights, having a double entry point to the MOOC from each of the two universities, determining shared ownership by both hosts, and the use of the USRN logo, since the network as such is not a member of edX.

Video production. Dealing with technical aspects of video productions was a demanding task that required efforts in terms of communicating those issues with all parties. This refers to the consistency of and among video formats, the way these videos were submitted, the quality of the videos in terms of content or length. In some cases language itself proved a difficult barrier since some of the staff involved in the production phase could not communicate in English.

Other similar challenges related to the levels of cooperation from internal and external stakeholders of each contributing university, in sharing data or offering visually appealing and learner-friendly materials, such as photos, videos, or other supplementing information.

At times, some partners shared materials through external websites, such as YouTube, rather than making the original data directly accessible or downloadable. This, in turn, affected the quality of some of the videos used in the course.

Scripts of videos for subtitles. Although the initial agreement was for all the contributing parties to share the scripts for all videos to be used as subtitles of the course, not all of them provided the scripts, which again affected the overall production.

The COVID-19 pandemic slowed implementation of the project at all levels. Internal communication in contributing universities slowed as lock-downs were put in place. Production of materials was delayed, as contributors were overwhelmed by the sudden shift to online mode. This affected overall responsiveness and communications. Social distancing and other protocols also affected the actual production, which in turn hindered the consolidation process of the whole course.

Midway through the production of the course, it was decided that a new *Special Session on Universities Response to COVID-19* would be added. Although this was not part of the original plan, consolidating the new materials into the course required a new series of communications, requests for collaboration, data gathering, and video production from the member universities. It proved to be a positive decision as it resulted in an enriching session portraying diversity in response from the universities.

Suggested strategies for building a collaborative MOOC

Building a collaborative MOOC is an exciting process. However there are always unforeseen challenges, based on the experience described in this paper, the next section of this paper offers suggestions for those who decide to embark on similar endeavours. Two levels of engagement will need to be considered throughout the collaborative process: (a) challenges faced by all contributing members; and (b) the difficulties faced by members leading the process.

Suggestions to all contributing members

Responsibility with one's own commitments. As a contributor in a collaborative project, individuals and institutions should remember that their timely response is essential in the whole process. Individual delays in delivering agreed tasks hinders the pace of the whole project. Collaborative efforts depend on everyone's prompt responses and inputs.

Initial promises should be realistic. The initial excitement of the project may lead to unrealistic expectations, thus it is crucial to consider feasibility and review one's own capacities in offering contributions before committing oneself or one's institution to a collaborative project. Good communication within one's own institution is a key in order to set up the framework and conditions to assure that tasks can be delivered, while also being transparent with the external stakeholders.

Gather one's own data and share it in time and form. Once commitment to a project has been made, the contributing institution should develop its own strategy to mobilize staff and resources to design, create and share necessary data. Contributing institutions should be certain about the capabilities and willingness of their own staff to participate in the project.

Suggestions to the leading members of the project

Fulfill your vision by accomplishing small tasks. Collaborating partners may have different ideas about what is expected of them. Thus, a clear message is essential. The overall vision will give a sense of shared direction, while a clear understanding of small deliverables and tasks will lead to concrete steps and achievements. A comprehensive and clear guideline at the beginning of the process is helpful.

Time management. As a leading partner one should consider three levels: (a) managing one's own time in relation to the goals and tasks required for the leading team; (b) setting up agreed deadlines with external partners to clarify when individual contributions should be expected; (c) benchmarking the processes at all levels: individually, with partners, and with the whole project.

Communication strategy. Engaging in effective dialogue with all relevant stakeholders is essential. The nature and hence the responses from your partners can be different. Colleagues in the academic world, for example, think and function differently from people working the public media. Hence, an effective approach will include common methods of correspondence (mails, calls, online meetings, etc), but also a personalised approach to each counterpart, for example in the time allocation to meet the needs of partners in different time zones.

Organizing the contents and messages that need to be delivered beforehand, having a clear agenda of topics, goals and expected decisions are a key to success. Keeping records and sharing the outcomes, through minutes or briefings is an effective way to track the process and maintain accountability.

Expect to invest extra efforts to mobilize partners. In collaborative projects like the one described in this paper, it is usually the case that unexpected issues will arise as original plans unfold. Although sharing and distributing tasks with partners is typically a core part of a collaborative project; as the leading member, one should be aware that motivation tends to wear out as time goes by, especially when requests are always changing. Having a cheerleading role is essential to keep the momentum alive.

Do not despair, be patient, be perseverant, be resilient. At times, partners are not responsive, even if they committed to cooperate and support the project at first. However do not assume that because partners are not responding they are out of the game. Motivation to remain devoted to the project may decrease as other priorities arise in their institutions. Persevere!

Friendly reminders and follow ups in calm and kind language on the importance of re engagement with and contribution to the project should be practiced. In some extreme cases, the leading team may decide to substitute a given project as the partners opt out in the middle of the process. Be prepared!

Conclusion

Universities are called to *do the work, show the work, and work the show*. This is a unique time in the history of higher education. IT solutions have made international cooperation in education much easier to expand and flourish. Communications are faster, taking place in real time, and the social expectation that universities should bring actual solutions to social needs is more evident than ever.

In spite of the apparent increasing interest and a growing convergence among different stakeholders in MOOC production, especially given the context of the COVID-19 pandemic which greatly boosted the use of online education and communication technologies, collaborative initiatives of the kind explained in this paper appear to remain limited.

An initial purpose of the MOOC presented in this paper was to encourage more universities to consider their pivotal roles in bringing change to local and international communities through promoting cognizance and visibility of the USR concept, its mission and actions. Within this context, this article described the creation process of a collaborative MOOC in a network of very diverse universities.

Emerging from why USR should be a priority in higher education; the paper provides an account of the steps the USRN took to produce this joint MOOC through an inclusive process that respects regional representation, diversity in meanings and implications on what USR is and how it is implemented.

USR is challenging traditional paradigms of how universities engage with society overcoming the traditional conceptions of the ivory tower. This debate promotes a more organic connection between what society needs and what universities can provide, bridging actual problems with solutions emanating from the academic strengths of these institutions. Giving back to and engaging with society is based on a new dialogue between universities, society and industry.

As an endeavor with global scope, the importance of the MOOC described in the previous pages lies in the fact that it brought together a range of universities to collaborate, and mainly because this course is the first attempt to provide an agreed frame that *contains and portrays* the so-called *third mission of the university*, the ways it functions and how effective strategies can be designed to promote the social impact universities can have.

Historically universities have *done their work*. They have made conscious efforts to accomplish their missions through the provision of education, preparing human resources to function as human capital in their communities while enshrining knowledge and producing innovative research outcomes. Emerging evidence shows that these missions have grown to include management and administration, and also the notion of giving back based on the idea that universities are usually financed by taxpayers.

Although the the teaching and researching missions are essential, only recently universities are becoming aware that *doing the work* is not the same as *showing their work*, that is, making society aware of their contributions, and bringing their knowledge out of the academic realms to make it accessible and usable to society as a whole, which for example can be seen in the increasing role of this knowledge in the connections to policy making at all levels.

The next challenge universities are becoming aware of is the need to *work their show*. Making their achievements socially visible and understandable to the general public is crucial, and for this reason, strategically putting their contributions at the center of the public scenario is a way to, not only maintain their legitimacy, but also to ensure their own sustainability into the future.

A decisive factor here has been the role university rankings play and how they shape social perceptions of the universities. This new factor clearly compels universities to display what they do (i.e. to *show the work*) in such a way that society at large can shape, own and utilize that information. This has made universities increasingly aware of the need to (a) gather and make their own internal data (academic achievements) permeable from and understandable to society, while also (b) being transparent so as to ensure their own institutional accountability.

In this sense the work carried out by the USRN in general, and specifically through the *Introduction to USR* MOOC, is to enhance synergies with regard to ways of promoting the universities responsible branding. The goal of the MOOC described in this paper relates directly to how universities in the network are working to bridge this gap.

This initiative served as a platform to accommodate a wide range of universities to share their own USR experiences; the project in itself was an effective medium to disseminate what universities do to achieve their missions, to produce synergy in promoting further collaboration among members of the network, and as such to *work the show*.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to express their deep gratitude to both the Center for the Promotion of Excellence in Higher Education and the International Strategy Office in Kyoto University, as well as The Hong Kong Polytechnic university, the USRN Secretariat, Ms. Miranda Choy, for providing this precious opportunity to conduct this wonderful project, and all members of the USRN for their contributions.

References

- Alzyoud, S. & Bani-Hani, K. (2015). Social Responsibility in higher education institutions: Application case from the Middle East. *European Scientific Journal* 11 (8), 122-129.
- Asia-Europe Meeting: ASEM Education (2017). Retrieved from <https://www.asem-education.org/about>
- Chen, S. H., Nasongkhla, J., & Donaldson, J. A. (2015). University social responsibility (USR): Identifying an ethical foundation within higher education institutions. *TOJET: The Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology* 14, (4), 164-172.
- Florentine, S. (2015). 4 ways MOOCs are changing professional development. CIO. Retrieved March 2, 2021, from <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1BFdP4S76tD2rbakOB5djVU5eXQsS0tOr/edit#>
- Futures, H. S., Andersen, T., & Larsen, K. N. (2020). A European approach to Micro-Credentials: Output of the Micro Credentials higher education consultation group. European Commission. Retrieved March 20, 2021 from <https://ec.europa.eu/education/sites/default/files/document-library-docs/european-approach-micro-credentials-higher-education-consultation-group-output-final-report.pdf>
- Haber, J. (2020). Leveraging the MOOC precedent in the age of COVID-19. The MIT Press Reader. Retrieved March 2021 from <https://thereader.mitpress.mit.edu/leveraging-the-mooc-precedent-in-the-age-of-covid-19/>
- Hersh, R. H. & Schneider, C. G. (2005). Fostering Personal & Social Responsibility on College & University Campuses. *Liberal Education*, 91 (3), 6-13.
- Hollister, R. M., Pollock, J. P., Gearan, M., Reid, J., Stroud, S., & Babcock, E. (2012). The talloires Network: A global coalition of engaged universities. *Journal of Higher Education Outreach and Engagement* 16 (4), 81-102.
- Hood, N. & Littlejohn, A. (2016). Quality in MOOCs: Surveying the terrain. Commonwealth of Learning. Retrieved February 23, 2021, from <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/2352>
- Impley, C. (2021). Massive online open courses see exponential growth during COVID-19 pandemic. The Conversation. Retrieved March 2, 2021, from <https://theconversation.com/massive-online-open-courses-see-exponential-growth-during-covid-19-pandemic-141859>
- JMOOC: Schools and partners (2021). Retrieved from <https://www.jmooc.jp/en/partners/>
- Kigotho, W. (2021). Social responsibility MOOC for universities launched. Retrieved March 20, 2021, from <https://www.universityworldnews.com/post.php?story=20210203142504450>
- McAndrew, P. & Scanlon, E. (2013). Open learning at a distance: Lessons for struggling MOOCs. *Science*, 342(6165), 1450-1451.
- McClure, M. W. (2013). MOOCs: Hope and hype in viral technologies and policies. *Excellence in Higher Education*, 4, 7-24.
- Palacio, F & Choy, M. (2019). Building a responsible brand in higher education underpinned by University Social Responsibility. In *Proceedings of the QS-APPLE 2019 conference: Industrial Revolution 4.0 and Aging Societies*. Fukuoka: Japan.
- Shek, T. L. D. & Hollister, R. M. (2017). *University social responsibility and quality of life: A global survey of concepts and experiences*. Springer: Singapore.
- Shumski, D. (2013). Coursera study reveals typical MOOC users. Higher Ed Dive. Retrieved February 23, 2021, from <https://www.highereddive.com/news/coursera-study-reveals-typical-mooc-user/197570/>

Working paper

Fernando Palacio - PhD. International Strategy Office - Kyoto University

Sammour, G., Al-zoubi, A., & Schreurs, J. (2019). Development of MOOC in Virtual Joint Academic Degree programs. In *Proceedings of the 21st International Conference on Enterprise Information Systems*. DOI: 10.5220/0007754806370643.

Tetrevova, L. & Sabolova, V. (2010). University stakeholder management and university social responsibility. *WSEAS Transactions on Advances in Engineering Education*, 7(7), 224–233.

University Social Responsibility Network (n.d.). Accessed January 14, 2021, from <http://www.usrnetwork.org/>

Vasilescu, R., Barna, C., Epure, M., & Baicu, C. (2010). Developing university social responsibility: A model for the challenges of the new civil society. *Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 2 (2), 4177–4182, 2010.

Viswanathan, R. (2012). Teaching and learning through MOOC. *Frontiers of Language and Teaching* 3, 32-40.